

IMPROVING THE PRACTICAL READINESS OF FUTURE MANAGERS FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada kelajakdagi menejerlarning sun'iy intellektga ega bo'lish uchun amaliy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish, Super ong, giperong yoki super-inson ongi haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar

giperong, kognitiv, Artificial, ISSEK NRU HSE.

Аннотация

В этой статье представлена информация о Сверхсознании, сверхчеловеческом или сверхчеловеческом сознании, чтобы улучшить практическую подготовку будущих менеджеров для приобретения искусственного интеллекта.

Ключевые слова

гиперонг, когнитивный, искусственный, ИСИЭЗ НИУ ВШЭ.

Abstract

This article provides information on Superconsciousness, hyperhuman or superhuman consciousness, to improve the practical training of future managers to acquire artificial intelligence.

Key words

hyperong, cognitive, Artificial, ISSEK NRU HSE.

INTRODUCTION

Training of selfless, inquisitive, innovative, enterprising, professional management personnel who meet the requirements of the times and forming their reserve is one of the urgent issues of today.

Artificial consciousness, artificial intelligence, or artificial intelligence (English : Artificial intelligence; usually abbreviated as AI) is the consciousness displayed by machines , as opposed to the natural consciousness displayed by humans or animals . Leading artificial intelligence textbooks define the field as the study of "intelligent agents": any system that understands its environment and takes actions

that maximize the chance of successfully achieving its goals. Popularly, the term "artificial intelligence" is often used to describe machines that mimic the "cognitive" functions associated with human perception, such as "learning" and "problem solving," but this definition is rejected by most AI researchers.

A supermind, hyperhuman, or superhuman mind, is a hypothetical agent with intelligence far superior to that of the most gifted human. Superconsciousness may also refer to the form or level of intelligence possessed by such an agent.

REFERENCES AND METHODOLOGY

Artificial intelligence is an important element of the fourth industrial revolution. Its rapid development and expansion of its practical application require "adding" this phenomenon to the field of law. The regulation of public relations related to the development and use of artificial intelligence is a complex task in one way or another, and experts have different views on which areas and activities should be regulated, and the proposed approaches to regulation differ in different countries. significantly different. Given the increasing importance of artificial intelligence, legal regulation of related issues will be on the agenda both nationally and internationally in the coming years. It is important to develop an agreed position among the governments of different countries in the formation of a legal regulatory bloc of artificial intelligence, for this it is necessary to understand the needs of creating such a regulation. This is an incentive to conduct theoretical research on this topic and create educational courses in the relevant direction. The issue of legal regulation of artificial intelligence and the problems arising from it are already being studied by students of the world's leading universities, for example, since 2018, the interactive course "Regulating Artificial Intelligence" has been included in the program of Stanford University. Intelligence), as the authors of the course, are designed to deepen the understanding of the current and medium-term problems of the future lawyers in this field. The course examines possible directions for the development of artificial intelligence, development using existing versions of artificial intelligence, various legal issues, and basic concepts of artificial intelligence regulation. In Russia, the new educational course "Legal Regulation of Artificial Intelligence" was first included in the master's program at the Nizhny Novgorod State University named after NI in 2020. Lobachevsky. Starting from 2021, a similar course will be taught to law students at the Higher School of Economics. at the Faculty of Law of Moscow State University named after MV. The course "Artificial Intelligence and Law" was created by Lomonosov. It can be said that in the next few years, academic subjects will appear in all Russian law schools

and law faculties of universities devoted to the legal regulation of artificial intelligence and its impact on law.

RESULTS

Two-thirds of top managers in our country plan to transfer part of their current routine and analytical tasks to artificial intelligence in the next five years. This comes from a study conducted by the Association of Managers together with the ISSEK NRU HSE (existing) scientific and technological forecasting center. At the same time, only 1% of managers are ready to completely replace themselves with robots.

Loss of jobs, automation. Some of the functional responsibilities, primarily routine and analytical, will be taken over by AI-based services in the next five years - this is the consensus of top management.

Sympathy. At the same time as the automation of processes, the opposite trend is observed: the leader's character, personal characteristics, such as compassion, willingness to meet employees halfway, "getting into the situation" of each person, come to the fore. This trend is a manifestation of a wider trend towards ESG principles, which are currently being actively discussed in the world and in our country.

Volunteering Closely related to the previous point, but still a separate topic, is charity and volunteering. If the company focuses on the applicant's similar experience, then it considers it part of its value system.

CONCLUSION

We remind you that according to the results of last year's survey, the ability to see opportunities in a complex, uncertain environment was ranked first among the main skills of a manager. Second - emotional intelligence related to the ability to recognize the emotions and motivations of employees .

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